

Obstacles of English Language Listening Skills in First Three Grades

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ABSTRACT: The study aimed to identify obstacles facing students in the first three grades in acquiring listening skills from the point of view of English language teachers in Naour District- Jordan. The descriptive approach was used. A questionnaire on listening skill obstacles was developed, consisting of (25) paragraphs, which was applied to a sample of English language teachers. The study sample consisted of (105) teachers. The results showed that the field of obstacles related to student, educational means and techniques came in first place, and the field of obstacles related to the teacher came in last place. While there were no statistically significant differences in the obstacles facing students attributed to the variables (academic qualification and years of experience of the teacher). The study recommended employing technological means and techniques that would raise the level of students in learning listening skills for primary school students in Jordan.

Key words: Obstacles, first three grade students, listening skill, English teachers, Jordan.

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1. Introduction

General background

The focus at the present time is on teaching and learning English, as it is considered the most important contemporary language. Students' mastery and proficiency in this language has become an important goal, because we need to teach our children an international language that they understand and use to interact with people. English is a global language in all social, economic and political fields, providing its learners with better job and educational opportunities, and allowing them exchange ideas and opinions with people all of the world.

The findings of studies conducted by Al-Otaibi (2019), Al-Najjar and Shihada (2021), and Al-Masri and Al-Hayla (2023) indicate a general weakness among Arab students learning English as a foreign language. These students face significant difficulties in

applying English effectively. Additionally, various studies highlight a pervasive weakness in English proficiency, particularly in listening skills, both locally and internationally, as evidenced by Rodriguez (2012), Al-Hosni (2014), Alrawashdeh (2015), Saada and Al-Dhamour (2017), and Al-Sa'ani (2019).

Modern educational models emphasize the importance of auditory skills in learners as the foundation of language. Linguistics also underscores the significance of listening for learners during the learning process (Al-Muawlia, 2021).

Shreyt et al. (2021) mentioned that listening can achieve various goals, which may vary from person to person. Notable among these goals are: developing the ability to listen attentively and focus on the auditory material in alignment with the child's developmental stages; enhancing the capability to follow spoken content; training on understanding the auditory material with speed and accuracy by monitoring the speaker; instilling listening habits as a significant social and educational value in individual development; fostering rapid thinking; and assisting the child in decision-making.

Literature, studies, and educational research have demonstrated that listening skills can be taught and that learners need to acquire this skill. Effective teaching of listening requires a systematic and scientific approach to impart it to learners. This necessitates the development of a curriculum for teaching listening skills, which should have specific objectives, content, teaching methods, and evaluation techniques. Programs should be designed to consider the types of learners, their developmental levels, and their needs. This also requires a knowledgeable trainer with a high level of cultural and academic preparation, who understands and is trained in this skill, and is capable of teaching and conveying it. This responsibility falls primarily on teacher preparation colleges and, more specifically, on colleges of education (Hassan, 2018; Shdeifat, 2023).

Ashour and Al-Hawamdeh (2007) indicated that establishing a fixed method for teaching listening can undermine the teaching process because methods are continually evolving and changing according to the specific educational context. However, there are relatively stable stages that can be followed in teaching listening skills: Preparation Stage: In this stage, the teacher prepares the listening material in advance to ensure it is suitable for the students' abilities, interests, and experiences. The teacher also selects the tools and resources that will aid effective listening. Implementation Stage: During this phase, the teacher highlights and emphasizes key points, providing opportunities for students to discuss these points in a manner deemed appropriate for the situation. Follow-up Stage: This stage resembles a feedback process, where the teacher assesses the students' understanding of the listening material by discussing with them what they have heard.

Al-Atwi and Al-Huwaiti (2017) suggest that students should adhere to certain behaviours to acquire listening skills. These include: Direct Eye Contact: Students should look directly at their teacher while listening to the explanation. Focus on Words and Meanings: Attention should be concentrated on the spoken words and their meanings. Minimize Distractions: Efforts should be made to reduce factors that could distract students during the listening process. Open-Minded Listening: Students should listen with an open mind and without bias. Note-Taking: Students should take notes while the teacher is

speaking to maintain intellectual engagement. Asking Questions: Students should ask questions after the discussion to clarify any points they did not understand.

There are numerous obstacles to effective listening that hinder the listening process. These obstacles can be related to the teacher, the student, the curriculum, or the educational tools and technologies. Based on the areas covered in the research study, they can be summarized as follows:

First: Obstacles Related to the Teacher: Al-Hashimi and Al-Ghazawi (2005) noted the teacher's mastery of the subject matter plays an essential role in attracting the listener's attention. Consequently, the teacher must exhibit the following qualities: eloquence, a strong personality, engaging presentation of material, persuasive skills, credibility, thorough knowledge of the subject matter, and a rich vocabulary.

Second: Obstacles Related to the Student: includes physical and understanding barriers that affect the process of effective listening. These can manifest as a student's inability to successfully engage in listening skills (Tahir, 2010).

Third: Obstacles Related to the Curriculum: Al-Shanti (2001) and Tahir (2010) pointed out that neglecting listening skills in the school curriculum leads to a lack of training for students in this important skill. Effective listening requires persistence and effort to master.

Fourth: Obstacles Related to Educational Tools and Technologies: Haitham and Al-Arous (2021) emphasize that one of the major obstacles to effective listening is the lack of access to technologies that allow students to hear a variety of voices and accents, which facilitates easier language acquisition.

The basic elementary stage is crucial for building and acquiring language skills, necessitating that students are taught language skills on a solid foundation. Given the significant role of the English language in contemporary life, many educational institutions have made teaching it as a foreign language a core curriculum subject for primary students. Consequently, it is imperative to choose the method of teaching English with great care and to employ teaching strategies that make the learning process more effective. The focus should be on utilizing the language for communication and comprehension, rather than solely emphasizing the literature associated with it (Al-Sanafi, 2022).

Several previous studies, such as those by Al-Atwi and Al-Huwaiti (2017) and Branch et al. (2016), indicate that students face obstacles in learning the listening skill. This is because schools tend to emphasize writing, reading, and vocabulary more, while listening is not considered a significant part of the curriculum. Additionally, most teachers do not give much attention to this skill in their classrooms. However, when teachers are aware of these obstacles, it helps them develop effective listening strategies, address these challenges, and improve students' abilities in this skill.

The study by Hadeed and Kneywe (2023) recommended further research to explore the obstacles faced by both teachers and learners in acquiring English listening skills. That is why the current study was conducted.

Objectives and Research Questions

The current study aimed to identify the challenges faced by first-grade students in acquiring listening skills from the perspective of English language teachers in the Naur district. The study sought to answer the following questions:

-What are the challenges faced by first-grade students in acquiring listening skills from the perspective of English language teachers?

-Are there statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$) between the mean scores of the challenges faced by first-grade students in acquiring listening skills from the perspective of English language teachers in the Naur district, attributed to the variables of (academic qualification and years of experience)?

Research Significance

The significance of this study stems from the importance of acquiring and mastering the English language, which has become a bridge for communication between peoples. The theoretical importance of the study lies in understanding the impact of variables such as academic qualification and teaching experience on the challenges students face in acquiring listening skills, which is a crucial aspect of the English language curriculum. Identifying these challenges will help address and mitigate them, ultimately enhancing the educational process. This study contributes to the field of educational sciences by providing valuable insights into English language curricula and serves as a specialized academic resource for Arabic and local libraries.

The practical significance of this study is multifaceted. It provides a list of obstacles faced by students in acquiring listening skills, which can be valuable for curriculum planners when selecting educational activities for English language programs. Additionally, the study's results are expected to benefit educational supervisors by highlighting these challenges, enabling them to make concerted efforts to address or at least alleviate them. Furthermore, the findings can guide decision-makers in developing and implementing training programs for teachers to enhance teaching effectiveness in light of these identified obstacles.

Limitations and Delimitations of the study

The current study was conducted on English language female teachers of first three grades in Public basic schools in Naour District, in the capital, Amman- Jordan, in the second semester of the year 2023/2024.

The generalization of the results of this study is determined by the validity and reliability of the study tool, the objectivity of the respondents in its paragraphs, and the comprehensiveness of the obstacles to acquiring listening skills.

2. Relevant Previous Studies

The researchers reviewed relevant previous studies related to the current study's topic and arranged them chronologically from the oldest to the most recent as follows:

Irma and Parepare (2020) conducted a study to investigate the challenges faced by English teachers in teaching listening skills in Nigeria. The researchers used a case study methodology and designed an interview tool. The interviews were conducted with a number of English teachers. The study found that students faced challenges such as poor vocabulary mastery, lack of focus, indiscipline, boredom, and issues with speaking skills. Teachers faced challenges including insufficient teaching experience and lack of professional training.

Nadhira and Silih (2020) conducted a study aimed to distinguish listening challenges in English among tall school understudies and reveal their causes in Indonesia. They utilized subjective and graphic expository strategies, planning a survey and interviews. The test included 100 tall school understudies from West Java, Indonesia, with 8 understudies partaking in interviews. The consider distinguished listening in troubles such as new words, discourse rate, emphasize, and hazy elocution. Causes included challenges related to students' foundation information and need of dialect hone.

The study of Sartika et al. (2020) aimed to know teachers' challenges in teaching listening skills to young learners. This is qualitative research that used qualitative method with interview as research instrument. The researchers selected two English teachers at SD Katolik Santa Theresya. The results show that there were some challenges that faced by the teachers in teaching English to young learners such as teaching listening, motivating students to learn English, and lack of textbook to facilitate the students' needs. In teaching listening; the teachers found the challenges such as the students were difficult to comprehend or understand when the teachers spoke quickly. The teachers had some strategies to solve the problems to motivate the students, gave attention and care with the students. Besides, using of text book is not related with the students' need becomes the challenges in teaching English.

Lestari et al. (2021) conducted a research to distinguish the challenges confronted by English instructors in instructing listening at a boys' school in Indonesia. They utilized a mixed-methods approach, planning an meet device with a bunch of English instructors. The results highlighted challenges related to students' mental variables, common information of the subject matter, vocabulary deficiency, need of instructive assets, and teachers' strategies for educating tuning in comprehension.

Mayanti et al. (2022) conducted a study aimed at understanding the troubles understudies confront in listening to English. They utilized clear explanatory investigate, planning a survey and interviews disseminated to a test of 31 eleventh-grade understudies from tall schools in Sulawesi, Indonesia. The results found that understudies confronted tuning in troubles such as frail lexicon, need of intrigued in English, articulation issues, need of concentration, quick discourse by speakers, and need of self-confidence.

Handayani et al. (2023) aimed to distinguish the challenges confronted by understudies in learning listening and comprehension aptitudes in English. Conducted in Indonesia, they utilized qualitative research about strategy and designed an interview instrument with a test of 15 understudies. The comes about uncovered challenges in sound-related comprehension such as the quality of recorded materials, social contrasts, emphasize, new lexicon, length of sections, listening speed, and outside variables like noise, which driven to issues such as vague instructor discourse amid instructive circumstances.

Al-Yabis and Al-Rawithi (2023) investigated the challenges of inaccessible English dialect learning amid the COVID-19 widespread from the viewpoint of primary school students in Al-Qwai'iyah, Saudi Arabia. They utilized a survey with four domains: listening, speaking, reading, and writing. The sample included 367 students from grades 4, 5, and 6. The study found that students faced significant difficulties, with speaking ranked highest, followed by writing, listening, and reading. The results showed no statistically significant differences in all skills related to prior experience in learning English.

Srejon and Sukanto (2024) investigated the challenges faced by English teachers in teaching listening in primary schools in Bangladesh. The study used both survey and qualitative methodologies, designing a questionnaire and interviews. The sample consisted of 30 primary English teachers, with interviews conducted with 5 of them. The study identified challenges such as the volume of content, lack of computers and projectors, and issues related to classroom environment and insufficient teacher training in teaching listening skills.

Current study differs from the studies by Irma and Parepare (2020), Nadhira and Silih (2020), Sartika et al. (2020), Lestari et al. (2021), Handayani et al. (2023), and Srejon and Sukanto (2024), which employed interviews as their data collection tool.

Upon reviewing previous studies, it is evident that the current study aligns with studies such as Mayanti et al. (2022) and Srejon and Sukanto (2024) in selecting a sample of teachers for data collection, However, the current study differs from studies like Handayani et al. (2023) and Al-Yabis and Al-Rweithy (2023), which chose a sample of students for their data collection.

The current study is distinguished from previous studies by its focus on variables unique to its context. Specifically, it targets teachers of the first three grades, a demographic not covered in previous research. To the researchers' knowledge, this is the first study in Jordan addressing the obstacles faced by first-grade students in acquiring listening skills from the perspective of English language teachers. The current study also benefited from previous research in selecting the appropriate methodology, sample, procedures, and in constructing the research instrument.

3. Methodology

To achieve the study's objective and answer its questions, the current study employed a descriptive survey methodology due to its suitability for the study's aims.

Participants and Sample Size

The study population consisted of all English language teachers in public schools covering the first three grades (1-3) within the Education Directorate of Naur District in the Amman Governorate, totaling 113 teachers, according to the Ministry of Education's statistics for the academic year 2023/2024.

A total of (105) valid samples were meticulously acquired for this study (105) as the study sample representing 93% of intended population. The distribution of the sample members was based on demographic variables such as educational qualification and years of experience. Table(1) illustrates this distribution.

Table (1): Distribution of Study Sample According to Its Variables

Variable	Level	Number	Percentage
Educational Qualification	Bachelor's Degree	68	64.8%
	Postgraduate Studies	37	35.2%
	Total	105	100.0%
Years of Experience	Less than 5 Years	23	21.9%
	5-10 Years	16	15.2%
	10 Years and More	66	62.9%
	Total	105	100.0%

Measure Instrument

To achieve the objectives of the study, a questionnaire was developed to identify the obstacles related to listening skills. The development of the questionnaire was based on the theoretical framework and relevant studies, including those by Saada and Dmour (2017), and Al-Otaibi (2019). The initial version of the questionnaire included 28 items, distributed across four domains related to listening skills:

Obstacles Related to the Teacher: 8 items

Obstacles Related to the Student: 6 items

Obstacles Related to the Curriculum: 6 items

Obstacles Related to Educational Tools and Techniques: 8 items

Validity and Reliability of the Study Tool

The initial version of the questionnaire was presented to a group of 20 expert reviewers with significant experience and expertise in curricula and teaching methods from both public and private schools and universities in Jordan, all feedback from the experts was carefully considered. Items receiving an agreement rate of 80% or higher were retained, while the remaining items were revised, rephrased, or removed based on the feedback. Consequently, the final version of the questionnaire consisted of 25 items (Appendix 3), organized into four domains as follows:

Obstacles Related to the Teacher: 6 items

Obstacles Related to the Student: 6 items

Obstacles Related to the Curriculum: 6 items

Obstacles Related to Educational Tools and Techniques: 7 items

Additionally, correlation coefficients between each domain of the questionnaire and the total score were calculated, as shown in Table (2).

Table (2): Correlation Coefficients Between Scores of Each Domain and the Total Questionnaire Score

No.	Domain	Correlation with Total Score
1	Obstacles Related to the Teacher	0.72**
2	Obstacles Related to the Student	0.73**
3	Obstacles Related to the Curriculum	0.75**
4	Obstacles Related to Educational Tools and Techniques	0.54**

Statistically significant at the 0.01 level

Table (2) illustrates that the correlation coefficients between the scores of each domain and the total score of the listening skills questionnaire range from 0.54 to 0.75. These values are statistically acceptable, confirming that the domains have a good degree of validity. This suggests that the questionnaire is suitable for use with the study sample.

The questionnaire was applied on a pilot sample of 30 teachers to ensure reliability, table (3) shows Cronbach's Alpha Reliability Coefficients for Questionnaire Dimensions and Overall.

Table (3): Cronbach's Alpha Reliability Coefficients for Questionnaire Dimensions and Overall

Variable	Domain No.	Domain	Number of Items	Cronbach's Alpha
Listening Skill	1	Obstacles Related to the Teacher	6	0.816
	2	Obstacles Related to the Student	6	0.743
	3	Obstacles Related to the Curriculum	6	0.722
	4	Obstacles Related to Educational Tools and Techniques	7	0.827
Overall	25	Total Questionnaire	25	0.846

Table (3) displays the Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficients for the dimensions of the questionnaire and for the questionnaire as a whole. The values for the dimensions range from 0.722 to 0.827, while the overall reliability coefficient is 0.846. These values are statistically acceptable and good for the purposes of the current study, indicating that the questionnaire has a suitable level of reliability.

4. Results

Results Related to the First Question: What are the obstacles that students in the first three grades face in acquiring listening skills from the perspective of English language teachers?

To answer this question, the means, standard deviations, ranks, and degrees of agreement for all areas of the listening skills questionnaire and the questionnaire as a whole were calculated. Table (4) illustrates these results:

Table (4): Descriptive Statistics, Standard Deviations, Ranks, and Degrees of Agreement for All Obstacles in Acquiring Listening Skills, Ranked in Descending Order

Area Number	Area	Rank	Mean	Standard Deviation	Degree of Agreement
2	Obstacles Related to the Student	1	3.97	0.74	High
4	Obstacles Related to Educational Tools and Technologies	2	3.97	0.78	High
3	Obstacles Related to the Curriculum	3	3.84	0.82	High
1	Obstacles Related to the Teacher	4	3.53	0.87	Moderate
Overall			3.83	0.66	High

*Low Degree (1.00 - 2.33). Moderate Degree (2.34 to 3.67). High Degree (3.68 to 5.00)

Table (4) indicates that the mean score for the obstacles faced by students in the first three grades in acquiring listening skills, from the perspective of English language teachers, is 3.83 with a standard deviation of 0.66, reflecting a high level of obstacles. The areas "Obstacles Related to the Student" and "Obstacles Related to Educational Tools and Technologies" have the highest mean scores, both at 3.97 with standard deviations of 0.74 and 0.78, respectively, and both are rated as high. The "Obstacles Related to the Curriculum" area follows with a mean score of 3.84 and a standard deviation of 0.82, also rated as high. Finally, the "Obstacles Related to the Teacher" area has a mean score of 3.53 and a standard deviation of 0.87, rated as moderate.

For the "Obstacles Related to the Teacher" area, mean scores for individual items ranged from 3.18 to 3.74. Item (5), which refers to the lack of training courses received by the teacher in teaching listening skills, ranked highest with a mean score of 3.74 and a standard deviation of 1.07, indicating a high degree of agreement. Conversely, item (4), which addresses the teacher's lack of conviction regarding the importance of listening skills, ranked lowest with a mean score of 3.18 and a standard deviation of 1.20, reflecting a moderate degree of agreement.

In the "Obstacles Related to the Student" area, mean scores for individual items ranged from 3.53 to 4.20. Item (4), concerning the students' limited vocabulary in English that hinders their comprehension of listening texts, ranked highest with a mean score of

4.20 and a standard deviation of 0.99, indicating a high degree of agreement. On the other hand, item (6), which refers to students' auditory problems that prevent them from distinguishing between sounds, ranked lowest with a mean score of 3.53 and a standard deviation of 1.11, reflecting a moderate degree of agreement.

In the area of obstacles related to the curriculum, the mean scores for individual items ranged from 3.44 to 3.98. Specifically, item (2), which concerns the lack of consideration for students' interests and preferences when selecting listening texts, ranked highest among the study participants with a mean score of 3.98 and a standard deviation of 0.93, indicating a high degree of agreement. Conversely, item (6), which addresses the weak alignment between the listening text and the associated questions, ranked lowest with a mean score of 3.44 and a standard deviation of 1.13, reflecting a moderate degree of agreement.

In the domain of obstacles related to educational tools and techniques, the mean scores for individual items ranged from 3.54 to 4.24. Specifically, item (1), which addresses the absence of specialized laboratories for teaching English listening skills in schools, ranked highest among the study participants with a mean score of 4.24 and a standard deviation of 1.02, reflecting a high level of agreement. On the other hand, item (5), which concerns the inadequate competence of both teachers and students in utilizing educational tools associated with listening skills, ranked lowest with a mean score of 3.54 and a standard deviation of 1.18, indicating a moderate level of agreement.

Results Related to the Second Question: Are there statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$) between the mean scores of the obstacles faced by students in the early grades in acquiring listening skills, as perceived by English language teachers in the Naur District, based on the variables of (educational qualification and years of experience)?

To address this question, the mean scores and standard deviations of the obstacles faced by students in the early grades in acquiring listening skills, as perceived by English language teachers, were analyzed according to the variables of educational qualification and years of experience. The results are summarized in Table (5):

Table (5): Mean Scores and Standard Deviations of the Obstacles Faced by Early Grade Students in Acquiring Listening Skills, as Perceived by English Language Teachers, according to the Variables of Educational Qualification and Years of Experience

Variable	Level	Number	Mean	Standard Deviation
Educational Qualification	Bachelor's	68	3.87	0.72
	Postgraduate	37	3.77	0.52
	Total	105	3.83	0.66
Years of Experience	Less than 5 years	23	4.06	0.63
	5 - 10 years	16	3.76	0.52
	More than 10 years	66	3.77	0.69
	Total	105	3.83	0.66

Table (5) shows apparent differences between the mean scores of the obstacles faced by early grade students in acquiring listening skills, as perceived by English language teachers, based on educational qualification and years of experience. To determine whether these differences are statistically significant at the level of ($\alpha = 0.05$), to verify the statistical significance of these observed differences, a Multivariate Analysis of Variance (MANOVA) was conducted, as shown in Table (6):

Table (6): Results of the Multivariate Analysis of Variance (MANOVA) for Obstacles Facing First-Grade Students in Acquiring Listening Skills According to Qualification and Years of Experience

Source of Variation	Areas	Sum of Squares	Degrees of Freedom	Mean Square	F Value	Significance Level
Educational Qualification	A1	0.80	1	0.80	1.06	0.31
	A2	0.76	1	0.76	1.44	0.23
	A3	0.00	1	0.00	0.00	0.98
	A4	0.30	1	0.30	0.49	0.49
Years of Experience	A1	0.85	2	0.42	0.56	0.57
	A2	2.42	2	1.21	2.29	0.11
	A3	2.43	2	1.22	1.83	0.17
	A4	1.32	2	0.66	1.08	0.34
Error	A1	76.47	101	0.76		
	A2	53.23	101	0.53		
	A3	67.19	101	0.67		
	A4	61.35	101	0.61		
Total	A1	78.51	104			
	A2	57.06	104			
	A3	69.69	104			
	A4	62.81	104			

Statistically significant at the $\alpha = 0.05$ level

(A1: Obstacles related to the teacher, A2: Obstacles related to the student, A3: Obstacles related to the curriculum, A4: Obstacles related to teaching aids and technologies).

The results of Table (6) indicate the following: Regarding the variable of educational qualification, there are no statistically significant differences at the ($\alpha = 0.05$) level across all areas (obstacles related to the teacher, obstacles related to the student, obstacles related to the curriculum, and obstacles related to teaching aids and technologies) for the obstacles

facing first-grade students in acquiring listening skills, based on the calculated F values (1.06, 1.44, 0.00, 0.49) and significance levels (0.31, 0.23, 0.98, 0.49), respectively.

Regarding the variable of years of experience, it was found that there were no statistically significant differences at ($\alpha = 0.05$) level in any of the fields (barriers related to the teacher, barriers related to the student, barriers related to the curriculum, barriers related to educational resources and techniques) for the obstacles faced by students in the first three grades in acquiring listening skills from the perspective of English language teachers. This conclusion is based on the calculated F values of (0.56, 2.29, 1.83, 1.08) respectively, with corresponding significance levels of (0.57, 0.11, 0.17, 0.34).

5. DISCUSSION

Obstacles of English Language Listening Skills in First Three Grades

Obstacles related to students were high

The result can be attributed to several factors. Firstly, the limited language skills of early grade students might lead to difficulties in understanding the language used in class, which can adversely affect their ability to comprehend the content being listened to. Additionally, the short attention spans and lack of focus typical of young children may prevent them from paying attention for extended periods, thus impacting their listening abilities. Moreover, there can be variability in response levels among students, with some responding better to auditory materials while others struggle with comprehension. Some students may also experience hearing issues that hinder their ability to distinguish between certain sounds produced by the teacher, resulting in distorted reception of speech and reduced interaction with listening activities.

This result aligns with the findings of the study by Nadhira and Silih (2020), which highlighted obstacles related to students' background knowledge and unfamiliar vocabulary. However, it contrasts with the results of the study by Srejon and Sukanto (2024), where the content of the curriculum was identified as the primary obstacle, with a shortage of computers being the second major issue.

Obstacles related to educational tools and technologies were high

Researchers attribute this result to the absence of specialized listening labs in schools. These labs offer a specialized environment distinct from traditional classrooms, enabling students to interact more effectively with audio materials. Moreover, the lack of variety and limited listening tools result in students' insufficient exposure to diverse types of audio materials that could enhance their understanding and development of listening skills. Additionally, the tools used may not align with students' needs—whether due to age appropriateness or comprehension levels—which diminishes their effectiveness. Furthermore, the limited use of blended learning in teaching listening skills is notable. Blended learning provides a comprehensive and suitable educational environment that fosters student independence and flexibility, allowing them to engage with audio materials at their own pace and skill level.

Obstacles related to curriculum were high

There are difficulties related to the curriculum due to lack of consideration for students' interests and preferences when selecting listening texts, the audio clip contains words that are ambiguous to the student, weak alignment between listening text and the associated questions, lack of audio aids accompanying the curriculum, the lack of logical progression of the curriculum content, failure to take into account individual differences.

Obstacles related to teachers were moderate

The researchers interpret this result by noting that teachers have varying perceptions of these obstacles. Some may believe that experience plays a significant role in overcoming challenges, while others might differ in their participation in training courses. Additionally, some teachers may still use conventional methods for teaching listening skills. Furthermore, the lack of effective guidance skills among some teachers could mean that students receive inadequate support for improving their listening skills. However, there are teachers who continually develop their educational, guiding, and interactive skills. These teachers strive to create a supportive learning environment that encourages students to learn and develop their skills in a comprehensive and balanced manner.

This result aligns with the findings of the study by Irma and Parepare (2020), which highlighted issues such as a lack of experience in mastering teaching skills and insufficient professional training for teachers. However, it contrasts with the findings of Srejon and Sukanto (2024), which identified teacher training as a significant obstacle in the domain of listening skills.

There were no statistically significant differences at ($\alpha = 0.05$) level across all areas obstacles related to (teacher, student, curriculum, teaching aids and technologies) facing first-grade students in acquiring listening skills regarding the variable of educational qualification and years of experience of teachers

Regarding the variable of educational qualification, the researchers interpret these results to suggest that English language teachers possess performance evaluation skills, given that teachers, regardless of their qualifications, have received training before commencing their teaching careers, in addition to undergoing assessments of their skills. Furthermore, the impact of supervisory visits and monitoring of teaching skills for all teachers may have played a significant role in the absence of these differences. The challenges students face in acquiring listening skills may be common across all students, irrespective of the teachers' educational levels. These challenges could relate to the quality of educational materials, the inadequacy of suitable listening environments such as school infrastructure, and available resources, which are the primary factors affecting students' listening skills, rather than the educational qualifications of the teachers.

Regarding the variable of years of experience, this result suggests that all teachers share experiences among themselves through a program known as the "visit exchange," which is organized and overseen by the school principal and monitored by educational supervisors. This implies that the teachers' perceptions of evaluating these areas were similar, and the visit exchange program was effective among teachers. It may be the case

that the challenges students face in acquiring listening skills remain stable and do not change significantly over time, and the effectiveness of traditional teaching methods for listening skills has not varied considerably over the years. Consequently, the challenges faced by students remain similar regardless of the teacher's experience.

Moreover, none of the previous studies addressed demographic variables, which results in a divergence between these findings and those of prior research.

6. Conclusion

The results showed that the field of obstacles related to the student and obstacles related to educational means and techniques came in first place, and the field of obstacles related to the teacher came in last place. While there were no statistically significant differences in the obstacles facing students attributed to the variables (academic qualification and years of experience of the teacher).

Based on the results, the researchers recommend focusing on listening skill in language instruction and directing teachers' attention towards it, training workshops utilizing technological and educational tools effectively showed be held specially teachers over ten years of experience Latest search recommendation was enhancing curricula with listening skill texts and associated activities.

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